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Al-Farabi National University (Almaty, Kazakhstan)*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15317860>**Abstract**

In mainland China, real estate companies often rely on loans from banks and other channels. As financial institutions raise interest rates to mitigate risks, liquidity in the real estate market tightens, leading to higher credit risks. This creates challenges for real estate enterprises in managing financial risks and ensuring steady growth. This paper focuses on Nanjing Chixia Development Co., Ltd. to evaluate its financial performance. It starts with an analysis of the company's basic condition and current performance indicators, then uses EVA (Economic Value Added) to assess after-tax net operating profit, total capital, and weighted average cost of capital. By comparing EVA with traditional performance metrics, this paper suggests optimizing the capital structure to improve financial performance. The study enhances the traditional evaluation methods and offers valuable insights for reducing financial risks and establishing a more scientific valuation system for the real estate sector.

Keywords: Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd;Eva index;Traditional financial performance

1.Introduction

China's real estate industry, as a capital-intensive and cyclical sector, faces long payback periods and rising financing costs, especially amid tightened policies and the COVID-19 impact. Traditional profit-based performance evaluations often fail to reflect true company performance. In contrast, EVA considers the cost of capital, offering clearer insight into long-term value. This paper applies EVA theory and traditional financial analysis to assess Nanjing Chixia Development Co., Ltd., comparing EVA with conventional metrics to highlight its advantages in evaluating financial performance.

Research by foreign experts in theory and methodology is relatively comprehensive, with abundant results. Marie (2012) demonstrated through case studies the differences in evaluation between the EVA perspective and traditional indicators^[1]. John Henry Hall (2018) argued that the EVA indicator is suitable for financial performance evaluation across industries^[2]. Quan Xin (2022) emphasized the need to clarify the theoretical foundation and application forms of EVA,

considering not only a single indicator but also accounting standards, tax regulations, and actual market conditions^[3].

Compared to foreign research, domestic studies started late and are not widely applied. The real estate industry, with its large upfront investments and long payback periods, should incorporate more indicators for consideration. Yan Dong (2018) believed that introducing EVA considers the cost of equity capital and protects shareholder rights^[4]. Sun Tianyu (2019) stated that optimizing resource allocation and improving resource efficiency are essential for enhancing core competitiveness, necessitating stronger performance management and evaluation^[5]

2. EVA-Based Performance Evaluation Indicator Analysis**2.1Net Operating Profit After Tax (NOPAT)**

As shown in Table 2.1 below, the adjusted NOPAT of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd has increased year by year, rising from 150 million yuan in 2018 to 300 million yuan in 2021. This indicates that the company is profitable overall and has achieved growth each year.

Table 2.1

Financial Indicators of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's NOPAT (2018-2021)

Unit: billion yuan				
Item	2018	2019	2020	2021
Net Profit	2.18	2.98	3.17	3.55
Interest Expense	0.16	0.11	0.2	0.25
R&D Expenses	--	--	--	--
Non-Recurring Income	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.025
Corporate Income Tax Rate (%)	25	25	25	25
NOPAT	1.5	2.5	2.8	3

Data source: Compiled from Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's annual reports (2018-2021).

2.2 Total Capital

Table 2.2 shows that Nanjing Chixia Development Co., Ltd.'s adjusted total capital rose from 16.306 billion yuan in 2018 to a peak of 23.23 billion

yuan in 2020, before slightly declining to 22.357 billion yuan in 2021. Overall, total capital showed an upward trend from 2018 to 2021.

Table 2.2

Financial Indicators of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's Total Capital (2018-2021)

Unit: billion yuan				
Financial Item	2018	2019	2020	2021
Average Equity	36.69	40.37	42.483	45.151
Average Liabilities	126.372	165.582	178.693	186.393
Average Accounts Payable	3.722	6.048	5.897	5.055
Average Advance Receipts	0.224	0.234	0.117	0.118
Average Taxes Payable	1.273	2.429	2.258	2.012
Average Employee Benefits Payable	0.067	0.071	0.072	0.081
Average Other Payables	17.334	10.693	16.669	13.454
Average Construction in Progress	--	--	0.0125	0.0112
Total Capital	16.306	20.596	23.23	22.357

Data source: Compiled from Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's annual reports (2018-2021).

2.3 Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)

Table 2.3

Calculation Parameters of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's WACC (2018-2021)

Item	2018	2019	2020	2021
Equity Capital Ratio	1.9	2	2.2	2
Risk-Free Rate (%)	2.2	2	2.2	3.1
Beta Coefficient	3.1	3	2.5	4.2
Market Risk Premium (%)	1.4	1.7	1.2	2.2
Cost of Equity Capital (%)	2	2.3	2.2	2.1
Debt Capital Ratio	0.56	0.55	0.7	0.62
1 - Tax Rate (%)	25	25	25	25
Cost of Debt Capital (%)	0.2	0.22	0.25	0.2
WACC (%)	1	1.2	1.5	1

Data source: Compiled from Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's annual reports (2018-2021).

Table 2.3 above shows the adjusted WACC-related indicators of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd from 2018 to 2021. The risk-free rate is based on bank deposit rates, and the borrowing cost rate is based on bank loan rates. The calculated WACC of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd increased from 1% in 2018 to 1.5% in 2020, reaching the highest value in four years. However, it dropped back to 1% in 2021, primarily due to the rise in the beta coefficient that year.

2.4 Calculation of EVA

As shown in Table 2.4 below, the EVA of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd increased from 134 million yuan in 2018 to 270 million yuan in 2021, with an overall rise of 136 million yuan over the four years. The EVA values from 2018 to 2021 were positive, showing an upward trend. This indicates that the company has some ability to create shareholder value.

Table 2.4 EVA of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd (2018-2021)

Item	2018	2019	2020	2021
NOPAT (billion yuan)	1.5	2.5	2.8	3
Total Capital (billion yuan)	16.306	20.596	23.230	22.357
WACC (%)	1	1.2	1.5	1
EVA (billion yuan)	1.34	2.2	2.45	2.7

Data source: Compiled from Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's annual reports (2018-2021).

2.5 Comparison of Net Profit and EVA

Table 2.5

Comparison of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's Net Profit and EVA (2018-2021)

Unit: billion yuan

Item	2018	2019	2020	2021
Net Profit	2.18	2.98	3.17	3.55
EVA	1.34	2.2	2.45	2.7

Data source: Compiled from Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's annual reports (2018-2021).

According to Table 2.5, the EVA values for all four years were lower than the company's net profit. The trends of net profit and EVA were consistent, with both increasing from 2018 to 2021, and EVA remained positive. This suggests that the company's economic

performance was relatively good during this period, and the utilization of equity capital was effective.

2.6 Comparison of Return on Equity (ROE) and EVA Return Rate

Table 2.6

Comparison of Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's ROE and EVA Return Rate (2018-2021)

Unit: %

Item	2018	2019	2020	2021
EVA Return Rate	76.05	77.28	73.82	61.46
ROE	11.1	9.59	12.92	9.32

Data source: Compiled from Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's annual reports (2018-2021).

From 2018 to 2021, Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's EVA showed fluctuations but remained relatively stable, indicating that the company's ability to create value for investors was steady. Additionally, the sudden impact of the pandemic did not significantly affect its overall operations.

identification. This study aims to offer valuable guidance for Nanjing Chixia and similar enterprises in refining performance evaluation.

3.Recommendations for Improving Nanjing Chixia Development Co.,Ltd's Financial Performance

First, establish an EVA-centered evaluation system.

Second, enhance asset operation efficiency.Implement a unified inventory management model.

Third, adopt a prudent approach to new project development.

Conclusion

By comparing EVA and net profit as performance evaluation tools for Nanjing Chixia Development Co., Ltd., the study finds that net profit fails to fully reflect operational efficiency. Longitudinal analysis shows EVA provides deeper insights. The study recommends improving incentive systems, enhancing asset efficiency, cautiously expanding new projects, and optimizing capital structure. Given varying risks across growth stages, real estate firms should adopt tailored financial metrics for better risk control and opportunity

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